

CHARACTERIZATION OF BACLOFEN NON-PROPELLANT TOPICAL FOAM FOR TREATMENT OF NEUROPATHIC PAIN

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ABSTRACT

To evaluate Baclofen non-propellant foams for physicochemical properties, stability, compatibility, and drug release for topical delivery. Baclofen was characterized by melting point, UV–vis spectroscopy, and calibration curves. FTIR assessed compatibility with excipients (SLS, HPMC, Carbopol). Foam formulations were evaluated for stability, expansion, retention, pH, drug content, moisture, and in-vitro release; release kinetics were analysed using standard models. Baclofen was pure and compatible with excipients. Optimized foams showed stable expansion, good retention, uniform drug content, skin-compatible pH, and sustained drug release via diffusion and polymer relaxation. The foams exhibited favourable physicochemical properties, stability, and sustained release, supporting their potential as effective topical formulations.

KEYWORDS: Baclofen, non-propellant foam, Pre-formulation, FTIR, Drug release, Topical delivery.

INTRODUCTION^[1,5]

Topical drug delivery system in order to provide targeted and sustained drug release at the location of pain, topical drug administration has become a potential strategy. This will increase therapeutic efficacy while reducing side effects. Because of their greater spreadability, ease of administration, quick absorption, and non-greasy texture—all of which increase patient compliance—foams have drawn more attention than other topical dose forms.

Non-propellant foams, in particular, are their safety for the environment, lack of volatile propellants, and regulated foam formation through the use of polymeric stabilizers and surfactants. By creating a solid, consistent layer that improves penetration and retention inside dermal tissues, these systems can efficiently transport medications through the skin.

Neuropathic Pain is a complicated, long-lasting pain condition is brought on by damage or malfunction to the central or peripheral nerve systems. Its symptoms, which drastically lower patients' quality of life, include burning sensations, hyperalgesia, and allodynia. Traditional oral medication, such as the γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA-B) receptor agonist baclofen, has been used extensively to treat neuropathic and spastic disorders. However, baclofen's short half-life, poor blood-brain barrier penetration, and systemic adverse effects such drowsiness, light headedness, and muscle weakness frequently limit its use orally. The necessity for new drug delivery methods that can provide localized activity with little systemic exposure is highlighted by these disadvantages.

Baclofen, being moderately lipophilic and having a low molecular weight, is a suitable candidate for topical delivery. Incorporating baclofen into a non-propellant foam system can potentially provide localized therapeutic concentrations at peripheral pain sites, offering an alternative to oral therapy for systemic neuropathic pain management. Formulation parameters such as foam stability, spreadability, density, drug content, and skin retention play crucial roles in determining the performance of the final product.

Therefore, the goal of this study is to create and assess topical non-propellant baclofen foams that are intended to effectively treat systemic neuropathic pain. In addition to evaluating medication absorption and retention in skin models, the research focuses on optimizing formulation ingredients, such as stabilizers, polymers, and surfactants, to produce stable foams with desired physicochemical properties. The goal of this strategy is to provide a neuropathic pain treatment substitute that is effective, patient-friendly, and ecologically friendly.

MATERIALS AND METHODS^[6,12]

MATERIALS

Baclofen (pharma grade) was procured from Yarrow Chem Ltd., India, and served as the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) for the formulation. Hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose (LR grade) was obtained from Shreeji Chemicals, Mumbai, and used as a viscosity enhancer and stabilizing polymer. Carbopol 940 (LR grade), also procured from Shreeji Chemicals, Mumbai,

functioned as a gelling and foam-stabilizing agent. Sodium lauryl sulfate (LR grade) was used as a surfactant and foaming agent to aid in foam formation. Tween 80 (LR grade) acted as a non-ionic surfactant and emulsifier to improve the uniformity and stability of the formulation. Glycerin (LR grade) was used as a humectant and moisturizer to enhance the spreadability and skin feel of the topical foam. All other chemicals and reagents used were of analytical grade and employed as received without further purification.

Preparation of Baclofen Non-propellant Topical Foam

preparation Aqueous Phase: Preparation of Gel Base: Weigh the required amount of HPMC and Carbopol 940 Slowly sprinkle it into approximately half of the total distilled water under continuous stirring while heating 50-60⁰C to avoid clumping. Allow it to hydrate and swell completely for 1- 2 hours. Preparation of drug phase: weigh baclofen and dissolve baclofen in ethanol and add tween 80 to this solution while heating until clear solution is obtained.

Preparation of Hydrophobic phase: In warm condition dissolve Sodium Lauryl Sulfate in small portion of water separately mix until clear mixture occurs.

Combining Aqueous and Hydrophobic Phases: Slowly add drug phase mixture into the hydrated HPMC gel base while continuous stirring and then add Sodium Lauryl Sulfate solution into the mixture and stir gently adjust the pH to ~6.5–7.0 using pH adjuster and add preservatives in required quantity. Add the remaining amount of distilled water to bring the formulation to the final required weight in a warm condition.

Packing: Fill the formulation into foam pump bottle (non-propellant or non-aerosol pump) which is designed to produce foam upon mechanical actuation.

Table 1: Foam compositions expressed in grams.

Formulation	Baclofen (mg)	SLS (gm)	Tween 80 (ml)	Carbopol 940 (gm)	HPMC (gm)	Glycerine (ml)	Methyl paraben (ml)	Cetyl Alcohol (ml)
1	200	1	0.377	0.4	0.2	0.317	0.042	0.247
2	200	1	1.13	0.4	0.2	0.317	0.042	0.247
3	200	1	0.377	0.1	0.2	0.317	0.042	0.247
4	200	4	1.13	0.1	0.2	0.317	0.042	0.247
5	200	4	0.377	0.4	0.2	0.317	0.042	0.247
6	200	4	1.13	0.4	0.2	0.317	0.042	0.247
7	200	4	0.377	0.1	0.2	0.317	0.042	0.247
8	200	1	1.13	0.1	0.2	0.317	0.042	0.247

EVALUATION TESTS FOR FOAM FORMULATION^[12,18]

The prepared non-propellant foam formulation was evaluated for different parameters like Drug-Excipients compatibility, Surface morphology, Zeta potential determination, In vitro diffusion study, and Stability studies as per ICH guidelines.

Foam Collapse test: Foam collapse test measure how quickly a dispensed foam collapses (loses volume) and quantify foam stability (collapse time) under controlled conditions. With respect to time taken for loses volume of foam collapse test done.

The collapsing tendency of the foam was examined after actuating one dose of foam (one pumping) from propellant free pump on the film layers.

The collapsing process was recorded on horizontal photos taken with the time interval. **Foam Expansion test:** The Foam Expansion Test, also known as the Foamability Test, is done to determine the ability of a foam formulation to expand and form foam upon application. It evaluates how much foam is generated from a known amount of formulation.

Take a 10 mL of the foam formulation in a clean dry 100 mL graduated cylinder. Seal the top with the stopper. Shake the cylinder vigorously for 25-30 times over a period of 1min. Immediately measure the total volume of (foam + liquid) in cylinder after shaking. Record the initial liquid foam volume and final foam volume.

Formula for calculation

Foam Expansion (%) = $\frac{\text{Volume of Foam} - \text{Initial Volume}}{\text{Initial Volume}} \times 100$

Initial Volume

Acceptable range for non-propellant foams is 300-500% usually considered as good.

Foam Retention test: The Foam retention Test done to evaluates how long a foam retains its structure after being formed. This is critical for topical applications, where the foam must remain stable long enough for application and absorption. To determine the duration and quality of foam retention after generation, expressed as foam stability (%) over time. Measure 10 mL of the foam formulation, Pour it into a clean, dry 100 mL graduated cylinder. Seal the top of the cylinder with the stopper. Shake the cylinder vigorously to 1min to produce foam. Immediately record the foam volume total volume or total height of the foam. Allow cylinder

to stand undisturbed at room temperature. Record the foam volume at specific time interval and time taken for foam to completely collapse or reduce to half of its original volume.

Calculation

$$\text{Foam stability (\%)} = \frac{\text{Foam volume at time}}{\text{Initial foam volume}} \times 100$$

Stability greater than 70% after 10min is considered good for foams.

Moisture content test: The Moisture Content Test determines the percentage of water present in a foam formulation. This is important because moisture affects the foam's texture, spreadability, stability, and drug release properties. To estimate the percentage of moisture in a foam formulation by weight loss on drying. Clean and dry the weighing container (e.g., crucible or petri dish). Weigh the empty container (W_1). Add a known amount of foam formulation (1-2gram) to dish and record the total weight (w_2). Place a dish in Hot air oven at 105°C for 1hr or constant weight is obtained. Remove the dish and cool for 15-20 min. Weigh the dish again (W_3) after cooling.

Calculation Formula

$$\text{MC (\%)} = \frac{[W_2 - W_3]}{[W_2 - W_1]} \times 100$$

Typically, moisture content in the non-propellant foam is 20-60 % depending on formulation.

pH Measurement of a Non-Propellant Topical Foam: Measuring the pH of a non-propellant foam is essential to ensure skin compatibility, stability, and drug effectiveness. Since foam is a semi-solid, aerated system, its pH must be measured carefully to get accurate and reproducible results. Calibrate the pH meter with standard buffer solutions (usually pH 4.0 and 7.0). Dispense a sufficient amount of foam (e.g., 10–15 mL) into a clean beaker. Allow the foam to collapse naturally for a few minutes to form a semi-liquid layer. Insert the pH electrode gently into the liquid layer at the bottom (not the frothy part). Wait for the reading to stabilize and record the pH.

Particle size distribution. The particle size distribution of the non-propellant foams was determined by photon correlation spectroscopy (PCS, Coulter Counter model N4 MD, Coulter Counter Co. USA). The non-propellant foam dispersions were added to the sample dispersion unit containing stirrer and stirred to reduce the aggregation between the foams. The average

volume-mean particle size was calculated after performing the experiment in triplicate.

In Vitro Diffusion Study. The diffusion was carried out using phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) as the receptor medium. A diffusion cell with a 3.14 cm² area was assembled, and an egg membrane was mounted without air bubbles and clamped tightly to ensure good contact. 2 mL of foam was placed in the donor compartment. 150 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) was added to the receptor compartment. The system was maintained at constant temperature and stirring speed. Samples (1 mL) were withdrawn at 60 min intervals (0–8 h) and replaced with fresh buffer to maintain sink conditions. Samples were diluted and analysed at 220 nm using a UV spectrophotometer.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

FT-IR spectra confirmed that all characteristic peaks of Baclofen were retained with no new peaks observed, indicating no chemical interaction with Sodium lauryl sulfate, Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, and Carbopol 940. Minor peak broadening was attributed to weak physical interactions rather than incompatibility.

The Baclofen foam formulation showed a particle size of 137.17 nm with PDI 0.205, indicating uniform dispersion in fig 3. Two peaks were detected at 141.14 nm (98.77%) and 6.62 nm (1.23%), with high transmittance (85%) and stable intensity. The nano size and low PDI suggest good stability and improved skin permeation. The baclofen non-propellant foam showed a mean zeta potential of –31.0 mV (peak –33.6 mV) and electrophoretic mobility of –1.6237 $\mu\text{m} \cdot \text{cm}/\text{Vs}$, in fig 4. indicating good electrostatic stabilization and uniform dispersion. Conductivity (0.286 mS/cm) and high transmittance (82.3%) confirm low turbidity and stable formulation. The foam has stable surface charge and good dispersion, supporting formulation stability and effective topical drug delivery.

Foam collapse varied significantly among formulations (F1–F8). Low SLS ($\leq 7\%$): F1–F3 had low collapse (2.75–3.75%), indicating high stability. High SLS (20%): F4–F7 showed higher collapse (6.83–9.75%), suggesting destabilization at higher surfactant levels.

Foam expansion ranged from 148–402%. F1–F3, F8: Moderate expansion (148–200%). F4–F7: High expansion (249–402%), attributed to increased surfactant and reduced polymer, allowing more air incorporation.

Low moisture (5.12–7.54%) in F1–F3, F8 → more stable foams. High moisture (15.79–21.27%) in F4–F7 → softer foams, more prone to collapse.

Moisture levels affected foam texture, stability, and shelf-life. Foam retention in F1–F3: Moderate retention (55.50–64.83%). F4–F7: High retention,(76.33–85.16%).F8:66.33%. Higher polymer content (Carbopol/HPMC) improved viscosity and foam stability over time. All formulations showed pH 4.83–6.17, aligning with skin pH (4.5–6). Minor variations were due to differences in polymer and surfactant content. The pH range indicates good skin compatibility and low irritation potential.

Fig.1: FT-IR spectra of pure drug.

In Vitro Drug Release of Baclofen foam formulations exhibited sustained release over 8 hours: Initial (1–2 h): 10–22% release — controlled onset, no burst. Intermediate (3–6 h): Up to 70% release. F4 showed the highest release (38.53% at 3 h; 70.18% at 6 h). Final (7–8 h): 79.23–93.31% release (F8 lowest, F4 highest). Surfactant-rich formulations enhanced release rates, while higher polymer content slowed diffusion, resulting in more controlled release profiles. Drug diffusion followed a diffusion-controlled mechanism, typical for polymer-stabilized topical foams.

Fig.2: FT-IR spectra of physical mixture of Baclofen + Sodium lauryl sulphate + Hydroxypropyl methylcellulose + Carbopol 940.

Fig.3: Particle size analysis for non-propellant foams.

Fig.4: Zeta potential of optimized non-propellant foams.

Fig.5: Foam collapse test of foam formulation.

Fig.6: Foam Expansion test of foam formulation.

Fig.7: Moisture content test for foam formulation.

Fig 8: Foam Retention test for formulation.

Fig 9: pH test for foam formulation.

In-vitro Drug Release Profile of Baclofen Non-Propellant Foam

Fig.5: In vitro drug release profile of F1-F8 formulation.

CONCLUSION

FT-IR confirmed chemical compatibility between Baclofen and excipients. Foam properties were strongly influenced by formulation composition. Zeta particle size confirm that the formulation is stable, nanosized, and suitable for enhanced topical drug delivery. Zeta potential confirms that the foam has stable surface charge and good dispersion, supporting formulation stability and effective topical drug delivery. Low surfactant levels produced more stable foams with low collapse and moderate expansion, while higher polymer content improved retention and sustained drug release. All formulations had skin-compatible pH and demonstrated effective controlled release of Baclofen over 8 hours, supporting their potential for topical delivery in neuropathic pain management.

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